

Analysis of Wordsworth's Poetry from an Environmental Perspective

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Abstract: Nature and man too have a dialectic relationship. This research paper aims to educate the present and future generations to pay heed to environmental problems and also to learn and follow Wordsworth's deep and philosophical thoughts. Wordsworth's poetry explores the symbiotic relation between human beings and nature with an acute awareness of the devastation wrought on it by human greed. The ever-increasing appetite of mankind is devouring all that is beautiful and vegetative around us. For Wordsworth, nature is teacher, guardian, nurse and philosopher. Eco-conscious poet like Wordsworth stressed on the interconnectedness of all life. Consequently, human beings can learn to live harmoniously with all creatures.

Key Words: Symbiotic, Relationship, Nature, Mankind, Harmoniously.

Introduction:

Nature and man too have a dialectic relationship. Human beings depend on nature in return, man tries to change nature, both positively and negatively. Consumerism, commercialisation have taken toll on nature. Man seems to be going away from nature. As the time progresses, he is progressively alienated from nature. This is due to the thinking that man is master of nature. Therefore, there is a need for having concerted efforts to recharge and redeem his connection with nature. Wordsworth fulfils this need by creating spiritual awareness through his poems. This research paper aims to educate the present and future generations to pay heed to environmental problems and also to learn and follow Wordsworth's deep and philosophical thoughts.

Environmental problems are increasing in both frequency and intensity. Man-made disasters are also on the rise due to wrong interpretations of technology and mistakes. Because of the industrial processes, there is rise of chemicals into the atmosphere and consequent degradation in the ozone layer. Chlorofluorocarbons are the primary source of ozone

depletion. Many countries are witnessing population explosion. Naturally, there is an ever-increasing pressure for natural resources. Farm mechanisation has resulted in rapid destruction of organic components of farming.

Significance of the Study:

Man is gifted with fine sensibility; therefore, his actions should always be in tune with nature's rhythm. His 'filial bond' and a harmonious existence with nature is possible if he follows environmental ethics proposed by Wordsworth. Primary objective of this research is to investigate subtle nuances of Wordsworth's nature poetry and the relation between his perception and imagination because this is directly or indirectly is relevant to his ecological vision. Man has always raised doubts related to his position in the great chain of beings. He knows well how to grow intelligence, but he doesn't bother about his perception.

The human beings are influenced by environment and also affect the environment by their activities. In the wake of development, the activities of human beings have resulted in environmental degradation. The study of environmental studies helps us to understand the environmental problems aroused in the name of development. So much so that, natural environment is of crucial importance for social, cultural and economic life of human beings. Environment is a natural capital and it enhances the quality of human life. The quality of life is also enhanced when people come in contact with nature.

Man's changing attitude and his greed for power have inevitably hampered his relationship with nature. Materialistic interpretation of the external world devoid of basic natural principles is not enough to find out concrete solutions for ecological issues. Hence, scientific exploration of environmental problems and humanistic elucidation of the general laws of nature are sufficient to maintain harmony with nature. Transformational messages given by Wordsworth in his poetry can be of great help in strengthening man's harmony with nature. The primary emphasis of this research paper is to create awareness among the readers.

Hypothesis:

Wordsworth's poetry explores the symbiotic relation between human beings and nature with an acute awareness of the devastation wrought on it by human greed. Central to our inquiry is Wordsworth's message of oneness.

Literature Review:

Literature plays a significant role in raising awareness about the environment through various means. Through various genres, writers are developing a deeper appreciation for the beauty and bounty of nature.

Authors like Amitav Ghosh, William Wordsworth, James Thomson weave environmental themes into their literary arts addressing environmental issues like deforestation, climate change, pollution etc. They do so by incorporating environmental themes into their literary arts. It helps to catch the attention of people to pressing environmental concerns. Moreover, their heroes often interact with their natural landscape to highlight the symbiotic relationship between human beings and nature. Their struggles, triumphs, and conflicts serve as allegories for broader environmental issues.

Moreover, some literary works contain factual information about the environment, ecosystems, and conservation efforts, serving as educational resources for readers seeking to learn more about environmental issues. Amitav Ghosh's compelling narratives and characterisation inspire readers to take action to protect the environment. Whether it's advocating for policy change, participating in conservation efforts, or adopting sustainable lifestyle practices, literature can motivate individuals to make a positive difference. Overall, literature serves as a powerful tool for fostering environmental awareness, empathy, and action by engaging readers on both intellectual and emotional levels.

Discussion:

In the context of Romantic tradition, Wordsworth's position is not just significant from historical or environmental perspective, but his poetry injects new doctrine and new insights within us. He acknowledges and ascribes morality and essential unity to all beings. He envisions the whole universe as an integrated organic system. The human and non-human coexist peacefully and enriches the tradition of environmental ethics.

For Wordsworth, nature is teacher, guardian, nurse and philosopher. He defines poetry as "Spontaneous overflow of powerful feeling" The spirit of spontaneity is given importance. This spirit was rather expressed by Keats 'the genius of poetry must work out its own

salvation in man”. It cannot be matured by law or precept, but by sensation and watchfulness in itself.

As Pope has hinted,

‘Those rules of old discovered, not devised,

Are Nature still, but Nature methodis’d’

It is enough to illustrate the basic difference in rules between Augustan and Romantic poetry.

There is an intimate association between Romantic poetry and the French Revolutions. The great outburst of 1789 sent a thrill of fresh life. It came as a prophecy for a new day. It’s blessedness and benevolence spread like a fragrance. As Wordsworth himself writes:

Of college studies and their set rewards;

Nor had, in truth, the scheme been formed by me

Without uneasy forethought of the pain,

The censures, and ill-omening of those

To whom my worldly interests were dear.

But Nature then was sovereign in my mind,

And mighty forms, seizing a youthful fancy,

Had given a charter to irregular hopes.

In any age of uneventful calm

Among the nations, surely would my heart

Have been possessed by similar desire;

But Europe at that time was thrilled with joy,

France standing on the top of golden hours,

And human nature seeming born again.

(Wordsworth, 1850)

The ever-increasing appetite of mankind is devouring all that is beautiful and vegetative around us. It clouds our perception for what is being sacrificed in the name of progress for human beings. A recurrent area of concern in the poetry of Wordsworth is that human beings have become so self-absorbed and self-indulgent that they can no longer think clearly and environmentally. This unchecked and relentless exploitation of environment has destructive effect on the society as well. The enormity of destructiveness of the society on the environment is described as “winds that will be howling at all hours”. This destruction is not seen stopping as result of any act of mankind. The change Wordsworth is hoping for will come in the form of mighty revolt by nature. To add to the danger, the change hoped for by

the poet will not come as result of initiative by humanity, but as an uproar by mother nature in the form of battle. The battle will bring forth a victory for the environment and stimulate a rebirth for the world.

Environmental study is very important in today's world. The human beings are influenced by environment and also affect the environment by their activities. In the wake of development, the activities of human beings have resulted in environmental degradation. The study of environmental studies helps us to understand the environmental problems aroused in the name of development. So much so that, natural environment is of crucial importance for social, cultural and economic life of human beings. Environment is a natural capital and it enhances the quality of human life. The quality of life is also enhanced when people come in contact with nature. The focus of this research paper is how the environment has a concern for all. It hopes to enthuse green consciousness and appeals to all to take care of environment and save the planet. A sincere attempt is made in this research paper to explore nature poems to illustrate the truth that man and nature have an essential symbiotic relationship.

The researchers have examined nature as a chief originality force, so mystical which could enable and enlighten human mind and soul. Man has deep connection with the natural world. Wordsworth like others does not believe in the ideology that man has dominion over fish, sea and animals. On the contrary, he has a spiritual connection with nature and constantly reminds us that man is a part of nature. Man is not foreign in the natural order. Different ecological viewpoints of other writers are also elucidated in this chapter as well. The greatest scientific progress is not going to help man to be more blissful, more peaceful, more loving and more compassionate. Man's consciousness has not grown at the same pace as his scientific progress. Our consciousness should be a little ahead of our technological progress. The imbalance between the inner and outer. The outer is easier and the outer is objective, the inner growth is a different phenomenon. Each individual has to find the truth by himself. (Yiu-Chung, 2002)

When you discover love for nature, your consciousness is awakened. You discover love, happiness, peace in the company of nature. The easiest way to be joyful and to get divine happiness is to be in association with the mountains, meadows, hills and groves and brooks. When he looks at these, his heart fills with joy. All life of Wordsworth is about his relationship with nature. Many a times, in his poetry we find a conflicting mixture of idealism and realism. Doing things with the pure feelings of worshipping nature, flowering of consciousness takes place and great peace is descended upon you. You feel one with the

nature. You feel one with yourself. This process happens within you as a benediction from nature. So, his advice to the materialistic world is to set right its relationship with the nature in order to live happy, successful and prosperous life. Wordsworth elaborates his themes of childhood, youth, old age, spirituality and nature. Following lines illustrates this point more precisely:

In the faith that looks through death,
In years that bring the philosophic mind.
And O ye fountains, meadows, hills, and groves,
Think not of any severing of our loves!
Yet in my heart of hearts, I feel your might;
I only have relinquished one delight
To live beneath your more habitual sway.
I love the brooks which down their channels fret,
Even more than when I tripped lightly as they;
The innocent brightness of a new-born day
Tis lovely yet;
The clouds that gather round the setting sun
Thanks to its tenderness, its joys and fears;
To me the meanest flower that blows can give
Thoughts that do often lie too deep for tears.”

(Wordsworth, 1850)

Conclusion:

Eco-conscious poet like Wordsworth stressed on the interconnectedness of all life. Consequently, human beings can learn to live harmoniously with all creatures. The interactions between human beings and nature should be based on respecting the life of nature. Human beings should not interfere with nature's ability to sustain all forms of life. He shows the path to humanity.

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